

Open Book Futures:

National Libraries Digital Preservation: Processes for Legal Deposit OA Books

Authors: See list inside

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Author list

Authors are listed alphabetically.

First name	Last name	ORCID	Organisation
Gareth	Cole	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7493-0137	University of Exeter
Jenny	Fry	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3110-1683	Loughborough University
Sally	Maynard	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9895-4229	Loughborough University
Holly	Turpin	https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0214-3883	Loughborough University

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Miranda Barnes	University of Cambridge
Rupert Gatti	Open Book Publishers
Ross Higman	Thoth Open Metadata
Giulia Carla Rossi	British Library
Jenny Mitcham	Digital Preservation Coalition
Toby Steiner	Thoth Open Metadata
Paul Stokes	JISC

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Acronyms

Acronyms are written out in full in the first instance, followed by their acronym in parentheses, and from there on in referred to by their acronym.

API	Application Programming Interface
BL	British Library
CC	Creative Commons

CC-ND	Creative Commons – No Derivatives
CIP	Cataloguing-in-Publication
COPIM	Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs
CENL	The Conference of European National Libraries
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
LAC	Library and Archives Canada
LD	Legal Deposit
LDL	Legal Deposit Library
LMS	Library Management System
MARC	MAchine-Readable Cataloging
MODS	Metadata Object Description Schema
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
NLCR	The National Library of the Czech Republic
NLS	The National Library of Scotland
NPLD	Non Print Legal Deposit
OA	Open Access

OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OBF	Open Book Futures
OCLC	Online Computer Library Center
ONIX	Online Information Exchange
PID	Persistent Identifier
QNL	Qatar National Library
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
RTL	Register-Transfer Language
SPARC EU	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition EU
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation

1. Executive summary

The purpose of the research that underpins this report was to identify current practices amongst National Libraries regarding the digital preservation of legal deposit Open Access (OA) monographs. The goal was to gain a deeper understanding of what the needs are for an international preservation network of National Libraries, and to better understand current practices, workflows and policy landscapes within which the National Libraries operate.

In this research we conducted process mapping workshops with five National Libraries including, the British Library, Library and Archives Canada, the National Library of Scotland, Qatar National Library and the National Library of the Czech Republic. These workshops have all been documented within this report as case studies and correlating process maps, the process maps are included as appendices. In these workshops seven workflow phases were identified in the digital preservation of OA monographs, these were: identify; acquisition; pre-ingest; ingest; repository management; digital preservation; and access. Each National Library then identified the various touchpoints in relation to these phases of their individual processes, which include external stakeholders, internal teams and departments and internal and external systems.

The main findings from these workshops and case studies are:

- Open access definitions amongst the participants tend to be focussed on OA monographs being openly available as opposed to being free of usage restrictions. Open Access status is not always recorded within the metadata and licences are not always made publicly available
- The steps before ingest in the preservation workflow of OA monographs involve increasing labour and resources, with lots of communication and sharing of information with publishers/individual depositors happening in these phases
- Digital preservation practices are often placed at the beginning of the workflow, implying a 'preservation by design' approach
- Several of the National Libraries we spoke to have either recently automated previously manual processes or are planning to, representing one of the many areas that are beneficial for National Libraries to share practice on in relation to the digital preservation of OA monographs

From these findings Open Book Futures has developed five policy recommendations for national and international policy makers:

- Legal deposit open access monographs should remain openly available under their original licence

- The open access status of a legal deposit open access monograph/associated deposited item should be clearly recorded in the associated metadata and catalogue records
- Open access licencing relating to the usage conditions of open access monographs, such as Creative Commons licences, should be documented and clearly displayed in cataloguing information
- Electronic legal deposit legislation should be passed for all National Libraries by their correlating government
- All National Libraries should have a mechanism for the open display and download of approved content associated with open access monographs and this should link to other records for the same work within the National Library systems and catalogue

From these findings and recommendations, it is concluded that avenues for further research include: how publishers and individual depositors prepare their monographs for legal deposit and further digital preservation; investigating the extent of the challenge of international English language systems and aggregators, and how this impacts on the identification and ingest of OA monographs in languages other than English; a comparison between a parallel route to legal deposit for OA monographs and processes that handle the legal deposit of both open access and closed access publications; and the role of National Libraries in advocating for good practice in the digital preservation of OA monographs. It is also concluded that several of the findings and policy recommendations in this report should be included in international National Library networks and forums and that adding these points to existing agendas would be a viable solution as opposed to a standalone preservation network.

1. Introduction to Report

Loughborough University is one of the partners working on Open Book Futures (OBF). OBF builds upon the work of the COPIM project (2019–2023) and aims to initiate a step-change in the ambition, scope and impact of community-led open access book publishing. Specifically, Loughborough University co-leads Work Package 7 (Archiving and Preservation), which is developing scalable solutions to help scholar-led open access presses and library repositories to digitally preserve open access monographs and their associated content (e.g. video, audio files).

One of the key goals of work package 7 has been to develop an international network of National Libraries. The purpose being to gain a deeper understanding of what the needs are for an international library preservation network, and to better understand current practices, workflows and policy landscapes within which the National Libraries operate. To achieve this a series of process mapping workshops were held with selected National Libraries participating in the National Libraries Network and additional National Libraries which were later recruited. Barnes (2024) provides an overview of the initial development of the National Libraries Network and the preliminary conversations that identified the need for the process mapping workshops.

This report provides a literature review regarding OA monographs and how they relate to and are impacted by National Library policies and procedures, electronic legal deposit and digital preservation. It describes the process mapping methodology that was used and presents the key findings of the research, taken from five case studies and process maps. The report summarises the current situation vis-a-vis digital preservation and legal deposit OA monographs. It concludes by providing practical incremental solutions to the challenges associated with the long-term digital preservation of OA legal deposit monographs. The findings of this report will be of value to a diverse range of stakeholders involved in the scholarly communications ecosystem, including National Libraries, institutional repositories, digital preservation services and policy makers.

2. Background Context

In this section literature has been reviewed around the context of digitally preserving OA monographs in National Libraries. This includes: an overview of different types of open access conditions and licencing for OA monographs; a review of the recent history of electronic legal deposit and some of the common challenges; and current National Libraries practice and policy regarding digital preservation and open access.

3.1 Open access definitions, copyright and OA monographs

As Open Book Futures is a project focused on open access book publishing, it is worth defining different types of open access status, how this relates to the focus on books and monographs and how this affects the context of this report about National Libraries and digital preservation.

Open access initiatives are generally identified as taking shape in 2002, with the notable example of the Budapest Open Access Initiative's declaration¹. Notably, for the purposes of this report, in this declaration two complementary strategies were proposed to achieve open access to scholarly journal literature: one being the means to launch a new generation of journals committed to open access, and to help existing journals that elect to make the transition to open access; and the other being tools and assistance to deposit refereed journal articles in open electronic archives and open access journals. This suggests the importance of the role of archiving and digital preservation in maintaining open access status.

In the August 2008 SPARC Open Access newsletter, Peter Suber discusses the two component parts of open access also included in the Budapest Open Access Initiative's declaration, those of online access to research literature being free of charge, and free of most usage restrictions (Suber 2008). Suber goes on to chart the different ways these two components of open access have been defined, ending with the terms "Gratis and Libre". In this context, Gratis OA meaning the removal of price barriers alone, and Libre OA meaning the removal of price and at least some permission barriers (Suber 2008). Although Gratis OA engages with the principles of making publications openly accessible to read online, Libre OA engages with wider implications of access relating to how open access publications can be further distributed and re-used. Libre OA also suggests the importance of licences in open access, which centre copyright and permissions in open access status.

In every country that has signed the Berne Convention (World Intellectual Property Organization 1995) author copyright is automatic and extends 50 years after the life of the author, though

¹ Budapest Open Access Initiative Declaration <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/>

outside of some user rights, there is variation on what this means from country to country (Morrison and Desautels 2016). This variation, particularly in the case of Libre OA open access publications, makes clear licencing imperative. Furthermore, regarding National Libraries and legal deposit, licencing protects publication permissions in cases where copyright may vary according to differing national contexts. A Creative Commons (CC) licence, the licence commonly used in open access publishing, provides a means to grant blanket downstream rights to create adaptations or derivatives. Authors using Creative Commons licences still have moral rights and may object to the derivative and request that the attribution be removed (Morrison and Desautels 2016). These objections and the scope of reuse mean that other licences for open access works exist, such as NoDerivs (also known as CC-ND) which allows readers to share work but not use it for commercial purposes or remix, transform, or build upon the material for distribution². Licencing in the case of OA monographs protects the 'Libre OA' status of such a monograph, providing a clear way for others to use, share and adapt works without needing to request permission each time whilst still retaining author copyright and certain rights.

The Open Book Futures project, and its predecessor Copim, focus specifically on open access books and monographs. As Horstmann says in *From collecting to connecting – the role of libraries in Open Access*, books have historically not been as central to the open access landscape as journal articles (Horstmann 2017). Horstmann also describes how libraries and universities have become engaged in open access book publishing and how this has been made possible by the simplifications introduced through electronic publishing (Horstmann 2017, p.). As mentioned in the Budapest Open Access Initiative declaration (2002), if access to archiving tools and open electronic archives is integral to achieving open access to scholarly literature, then the long-term digital preservation of OA monographs is at the heart of protecting open access status.

Since the focus on OA monographs necessitates a focus on the existing mechanisms to digitally preserve books, this inevitably centres the role of legal deposit and National Libraries in this digital preservation. Furthermore, as OA monographs by their accessible and interoperable nature are publications with a digital edition, this leads to the consideration of the successes and challenges of the recent history of electronic deposit in the National Library landscape.

3.2 Electronic deposit and long-term preservation of OA monographs in National Libraries

In the British context, legal deposit has existed in English law since 1662 and helps to ensure that the nation's published output is collected systematically to preserve the material for use by future generations and to make it available for readers within the legal deposit libraries (Pedley 2019). Across the five case studies in this research individual histories of legal deposit are considered

² Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>

and whilst some differ, generally collections have been built under long-standing legal deposit legislation to preserve the intellectual memory and cultural heritage of a nation for future generations. Although there is a long history of legal deposit legislation, which is predominantly based in print media, as digital publishing and communications have rapidly increased in the 21st century, so too has the need to preserve our collective digital memory (Brindley 2009). Therefore, over the previous 20 years, National Libraries and legislators have been concerned with not only changing national legislation to extend legal deposit to non-print publications (Brazier 2016) but also to developing sustainable routes for electronic legal deposit.

Early publications on electronic legal deposit include Stephens and Gibby's journal article *National Implementations of Electronic Legal Deposit* based on a 2009 British Library survey of The Conference of European National Libraries (CENL) members and other National Libraries such as Canada, the US, Australia, Japan and New Zealand (Stephens and Gibby 2011). In this survey 72% of respondents stated that legislation for electronic deposit had already been passed in their country, whereas 82% of respondents had implemented it (Stephens and Gibby 2011, p.59). Although this appears to suggest that electronic deposit had been largely universally developed at this time, it should be noted that this original survey is limited in scope and lacks representation in Asia, the Middle East and Africa. Towards the end of their analysis of the survey results, Stephens and Gibby suggest there are two distinct approaches to accessing these electronically deposited publications amongst the National Libraries, that of replicating the access of print legal deposit by limiting access to on-site users within the library, and that of allowing deposited 'free' material to be made available remotely through web archives. They further suggest in their conclusions that "there is little purpose in collecting material unless it can be made accessible. It would appear from responses that the terms of access for research are similar, or in many cases more generous, than for example those that have been proposed for the same categories of e-material in the UK." (Stephens and Gibby 2011, p.61). This early analysis of electronic deposit remains relevant to contemporary conversations on the subject, suggesting a diverse and uneven progression in this area across varied national contexts.

In 2016 De Beer, Van der Merwe, Ball and Fourie conducted a systematic literature review about electronic legal deposit, specifically regarding books. In this review they identify seven of the main challenges documented across the literature including: legal deposit legislation and institutional policy; legal and ethical considerations; environmental factors; establishing mechanisms for depositing; human resources; financial implications; and trust. In the area of legal deposit legislation and institutional policy, a particular concern that is highlighted is how continuous developments in technology and publishing could result in legislation needing to be regularly revisited as "territoriality as claimant for legal deposit compliance becomes highly contentious when the electronic book exists exclusively, geographically independently 'in the cloud'" (De Beer, Van der Merwe, Ball and Fourie 2016, p. 92).

Regarding legal and ethical considerations, De Beer et al. (2016) specifically mention open access publications, suggesting this as a concern across the literature particularly in what it means for copyright, authors' rights and intellectual property. Another concern raised in relation to this is the proliferation of AI and a fear of machine-readable forms and how this may affect some of these areas. In response to some of these concerns across the literature De Beer et al. state that,

“though freely available, OA material is still material that has been published and needs to go through the same mechanisms for depositing as other material. This is very important to enhance effective organisation and access. As there are different OA models, depositories should be aware of the model applied to specific material and whether any additional usage rights apply. They should also keep up to date with the developments in OA – and by implication electronic books in OA” (p. 92-93).

This mention of usage rights also relates to concerns around copyright and is referenced by De Beer et al. through Kumbhar (2012), “copyright and DRM are issues that will still be discussed for years to come; if not addressed, copyright and intellectual property rights issues have the potential to prevent preservation” (Moghaddam, 2010). In the context of this research, these concerns are particularly relevant to how they might impact upon the digital preservation lifecycle of an OA monograph.

Another recent review of electronic legal deposit has been documented by Gooding and Terras in their 2019 book *Electronic Legal Deposit: Shaping Library Collections of the Future*. Across the chapters of this book are opinions and case studies from a large variety of National Libraries, including libraries outside of Europe and the countries included in Stephens and Gibby's (2011) article, such as Mexico and Zimbabwe. In their concluding chapter, which reflects on these case studies across electronic legal deposit, Gooding and Terras argue that although the 'reference-only' nature of non-print legal deposit has been important in maintaining publisher support, this negotiated compromise is challenged by changes in copyright, academic publishing, data science, and digital research. The authors go on to say that therefore “the solution is for the 'datafication of the legal deposit library,' which is built on the understanding that key legal deposit reference collections, including the UKLDWA, have been impacted by the digital turn in ways that undermine the assumptions that underpin their protections” (Gooding and Terras 2019, p.221).

As part of this solution, it is argued that “it is particularly important to differentiate between material that is open access, and that which is only freely available” whilst recognising the burden placed on libraries “to create and police differentiated access and reuse systems” (Gooding and Terras 2019, p. 222). These conclusions, although suggesting that open access definitions and licencing pose a challenge for National Libraries, emphasise the relevance this holds to wider electronic legal deposit practices and policies. All the publications referred to in this section on electronic legal deposit also emphasise the disparity between some electronic legal deposit legislation and processes, and the philosophy behind legal deposit.

3.3 Current National Libraries Policy and Practice Landscape vis-a-vis OA monographs

In addition to the literature discussed in chapter 3.2, National Library network and advocacy organisations the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) and the Conference of European National Librarians (CENL) have both released documentation and papers in 2024 and 2025 about legal deposit and electronic legal deposit.

In 2024 IFLA hosted the online event *Legal Deposit: A Strategic Tool for Building Tomorrow's Heritage* (IFLA 2024) which included contributions from the National Library of Australia, the National Library of Latvia, Sarawak State Library, Malaysia, the National Library of Scotland, the National Library of New Zealand, the National Library of Estonia, The National Library of Czech Republic, the German National Library and The British Library. The event included two sections: 'Inclusive Legal Deposit and Engagement'; and 'The (Long) Road to e-Legal Deposit'. As part of 'Inclusive Legal Deposit and Engagement', contributions covered topics related to publisher outreach strategies and collection policies of various National Libraries, as impacted by an increase in independent publishers and digital publishing practices. As well as emphasising the limitations of some legal deposit legislation with regards to the widest range of publishers, these contributions also emphasise the ways in which National Libraries are engaging with publishers and the proactive approach taken to expanding National Library collections. As part of 'The (Long) Road to e-Legal Deposit', contributions covered topics related to electronic legal deposit and its legislation, as well as adapting this legislation and practice for new formats such as AI as well as digital formats including podcasts and music. These contributions emphasise the continued difference and variation in the status of electronic legal deposit legislation, as well as the implications that electronic deposit has for emerging digital formats and how this impacts preservation practices.

In the Conference of European National Librarians (CENL) 2025 publication *Digital Cultural Heritage or: E-Legal Deposit in European National Libraries* (Oehlschläger and Wenzel 2025), the papers included cover similar topics to the IFLA event, as well as papers focussed on the importance of, and commitment to, digital preservation such as Arnold-Stratford's paper 'The Inspiration of Collecting and Preserving our Nations' Written Heritage – Findings of the 2023 UK Symposium' and Chuylan's paper 'E-Legal Deposit in Armenia – Ensuring the Preservation of Digital Publications'. The papers included in this publication, and in the IFLA event, not only emphasise National Libraries' focus on and developing practices in digital preservation, but also the continuous sharing of practice amongst National Libraries, particularly in these areas of electronic legal deposit and digital preservation.

In the 2016 article *Functions, tasks and roles of national libraries in the 21st century*, following a survey of National Libraries and work with IFLA, Stephens emphasises the importance of sharing practice in developing policy and procedures at National Libraries. Stephens concludes that exemplary practice and case studies are key to the empirical approach required for National

Library guidelines and standards, as it would be inappropriate to develop prescriptive guidelines and standards across the diverse national contexts in which libraries operate (Stephens 2016). Although in *The future of national libraries* Aramburo (2019) emphasises that the purpose and mission of National Libraries will always be intrinsically linked to legal deposit, and “the conservation and transmission of the creativity and knowledge that each country is capable of generating” (Aramburo 2019, p. 226), Aramburo also argues that this challenge necessitates a need to adapt quickly and intelligently to the current environment. As part of this point Aramburo also highlights the importance of collaboration with all involved stakeholders, as strategies for adapting to the current environment cannot be developed in isolation.

Using Sweden as an example, Hagerlid (2011) argues that as well as the ‘traditional’ mission of legal deposit, National Libraries may also hold the role of national research authority. Hagerlid goes on to elaborate the potential within this role of supporting open access agendas, both in advancing this agenda and in developing a digital research information infrastructure. This potential is due to the National Library’s position as being closer to national policy making, but also as an unbiased party in relation to the interests of the various stakeholders (Hagerlid 2011).

The literature on the policy and practice of National Libraries therefore supports both the notion that National Libraries in the contemporary moment are widely engaged in sharing practice through networks, but also that they are in a position outside of these networks to advocate more widely not only on issues of digital preservation, but also more specifically on the digital preservation of OA monographs and content.

4. Methodology

This research used process mapping to identify the policies, processes, and workflows deployed by National Libraries for the acquisition and long-term preservation of OA monographs in the context of legal deposit legislation. The process mapping was used within a comparative case study design that enabled development of an in-depth understanding of the workflows within each of the National Libraries that participated in the research. The resulting process maps enabled workflows to be compared across the participating National Libraries to identify challenges and opportunities for shared approaches.

The international nature of the National Library network meant that most of the workshops were held online, with only one of the workshops being held in a hybrid manor on the premises of the National Library. We worked closely with our contacts at each National Library to identify the relevant participants to enable the research team to fully map and understand current processes relating to digital legal deposit and handling of digital monographs through the National Library system. This level of local coordination was essential given that National Libraries vary in their organisational structures and the ways in which tasks and expertise are distributed across the organisation.

Ahead of each workshop the following preparation questions were circulated to participants:

1. What is the ingest pathway for an OA monograph to get into the collections?
 - Is there a difference between legal deposit and non-legal deposit?
2. What happens next? Think about the steps you go through in your area.
 - What systems do you use?
 - What ownership/responsibility do you have over the monograph files/content as this moves through your area/system? Is this transferred/assigned to someone else in the same system/area after your contact with it?
 - Is there anything else you can tell us about the process that takes place while you/your area have ownership of the content/files?
3. What process data do you capture and with / in what system(s)?
 - What data is viewed?
 - What data is generated?
 - What data is outputted?
4. Is there anything else you can tell us about the process that takes place whilst the content / files are being handled within your department?

Each workshop commenced by capturing the high-level stages in the end-to-end process, which is typical when using a process mapping approach. The various internal and external stakeholders directly involved in those end-to-end stages were then identified. Having established what is essentially a matrix of stages (across the horizontal axis) and organisations, departments, IT systems and services (down the vertical axis) participants were asked to identify and explain the various ‘touchpoints’ where the horizontal and vertical axes came together as a digital legal deposit OA monograph would journey through the end-to-end process.

The workshops took place between January 2025 and January 2026. Therefore, the workflows and processes described in the case studies, whilst accurate at the time of writing, may have since changed or been updated.

5. Case Study I – The British Library

5.1 Preamble

Founded in 1973 the British Library is one of six legal deposit libraries serving the UK and Ireland. The other five legal deposit libraries serving the British Isles are the National Library of Scotland, National Library of Wales, Bodleian Libraries (University of Oxford), Cambridge University Library and Trinity College Dublin Library. The British Library is a partner in the Open Book Futures project and is a member of the National Libraries Network.

5.2 Participants

The following roles and departments were represented by British Library staff in the focus group: Head of Contemporary British and Irish Publications, Curator of Digital Publications, Scholarly Communications Lead and Scholarly Communications Specialist, Head of Content Acquisition, Heads of Metadata Services, Digital Print Operation Manager, Legal Deposit Publisher Liaison, Scholarly Communications Lead, and Digital Preservation Research Lead.

Each of these roles represent the various touchpoints in the digital preservation lifecycle that an OA monograph moves through at the British Library.

5.3 Findings

5.3.1 Phases and touchpoints

Seven high level workflow phases were identified relating to digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs. These were:

1. Identify
2. Acquire
3. Pre-ingest
4. Ingest
5. Repository management
6. Digital preservation
7. Access

The ‘touchpoints’³ pertaining to these seven workflow phases involve a mix of internal and external stakeholders, such as ‘business’ units within the BL, publishers, other UK legal deposit libraries and end users. Figure 1 below illustrates these touchpoints in relation to the seven high level workflow phases.

Ahead of the focus group with the BL, which was the first in a series of workshops with National Libraries, the researchers drafted a template workflow process based on the previous work of work package 7 across the OBF and COPIIM projects to provide a starting point for the discussions. This template workflow was adapted and nuanced during the BL focus group. The main point to note here is that the initial template workflow started with ingest as the first phase, whereas during the BL focus group it became apparent that there are phases relevant to digital preservation that precede ingest. The preceding phases are: (1) identification of material; (2) acquisition of that material and; (3) pre-ingest preparation of material.

Each of the seven phases are discussed in turn below in relation to the relevant touchpoints in the workflow process map shown in figure 1, the process map can also be viewed in appendix 1.

5.3.2 Identify

There are different routes by which legal deposit books are identified. Under legal deposit law in the UK the onus is on authors / creators / publishers to submit ‘publications’ to one of the legal deposit libraries. The practice currently in place is for publishers to push content to legal deposit libraries, the BL in this case, but relying on publishers in this way can result in gaps in what the BL holds regarding legal deposit. As a supplement to the push content via publishers, the BL has web crawlers programmed to discover relevant publications based on specified seed URLs. Once per year the UK Web Archive carries out a whole domain crawl for websites with .uk, .cymru and .scot URLs. In addition, the UK Web Archive conducts frequent crawls for thousands of UK websites identified as holding content of interest to research and culture.

5.3.3 Acquisition

Legal deposit books are acquired in several ways. For digital deposit, the predominant way is for publishers to make an agreement with the BL to deposit content. In this agreement the publisher and BL agree that the preferred format for deposit (where works are produced in both print and digital format) will be digital. The agreement may also include practical matters relating to deposit and can also include deposit of back files.

³ As explained in the methodology chapter the term ‘touchpoints’ is used to identify and describe the points within and across the various phases where any given OA monograph will ‘interact’ with a system, sub-system, process or policy.

Figure 1

By prior arrangement publishers can bulk deposit content to the BL via File Transfer Protocol (SFTP). Digital files deposited in this way include the following documents: the book, the book's cover image, and the metadata file. Publishers who do not have the resources / infrastructure to bulk deposit digital books can do so via BL's Publisher Portal or via email.

Currently, one of the main issues in digitally preserving OA monographs is the lack of a standardised way for libraries, archives, publishers and third-party digital preservation services to tag book files as being open access. For the British Library this issue is compounded for legal deposit OA monographs because UK legal deposit legislation is ‘closed access by default’⁴. This means that for the acquisition routes described above it is not possible to maintain the open access status of a legal deposit monograph as it moves through the digital preservation workflow.

The UK Web Archive is used to collect government publications. Currently, librarians and curators identify web pages and sites that routinely publish with Open Government Licenses and flag these in the curator tool. The flag then ensures that all content collected at this level (and child pages and documents) are included as openly accessible content. Consequently, the BL is then able to maintain the open status of the relevant government documents throughout the digital preservation workflow.

5.3.4 Pre-ingest

The pre-ingest phase is necessary to carry out automated validation checks on the deposited data and to back-up the data ahead of it being processed. The back up of deposited data is typically held for six months to mitigate any issues that may arise during the ingest process. This results in a duplicate copy of the data, which is archived whilst the original version is processed for ingest.

Anomalies or exceptions are flagged during the automated validation processes and then checked by a member of staff.

During the pre-ingest phase the Metadata Services team will ‘normalise’ book data in readiness for ingest. Most of the digital LD content normalisation is completed to standards such as Ingram’s CoreSource⁵ and ONIX⁶ 2.1 or 2.3. It was noted during the focus group discussion that this step in the process requires intensive resource.

5.3.5 Ingest

Metadata is a critical element of ingesting digital book files for discoverability and long-term digital preservation. Publishers who have the resource and infrastructure to bulk deposit books will also deposit the associated metadata files. Not all publishers are able to create the necessary metadata in a standardised format, so for these publishers the BL uses third-party aggregators that provide metadata that have been normalised into acceptable metadata standards.

⁴ Interpretation of UK legal deposit regulations has not taken into account OA licensing.

⁵ The webpages for Ingram’s CoreSource can be found here <https://coresource.ingramcontent.com/ui/auth/login>

⁶ ONIX is an XML format for sharing bibliographic data pertaining to both traditional books and eBooks, allowing publishers to create and manage metadata.

Alternatively, for publishers using publisher submission portal, BL cataloguers may enhance records in some cases.

5.3.6 Repository management

Once the digital book file and the metadata file associated with it have been processed at the ingest phase it is automatically sent to the BL repository. The file package is then outputted to update or reconcile with the library management system (LMS). As a clarification, discussions referencing the British Library's repository indicate an internal system. This is not an open access repository, but instead is a closed-access repository internal to the BL.

The metadata is converted into MARC⁷ XML, with a matching record loaded onto the LMS to reflect what has been ingested (which then forms the basis of the catalogue record).

The repository outputs the record, which contains links to the ingested file in order to provide availability. During this process, identifiers are applied to the record and files around access.

Once in ALEPH (BL's catalogue), the catalogue aggregates the data for the content and publishes an output to other Legal Deposit libraries. Each copy is published to a different space. The content is securely networked in order for the content to be discoverable.

The LMS (Library Management System) is automated, so not within a "team" per se. But any exceptions that arise are dealt with by the Metadata Services team. The overarching responsibility for the LMS resides within collection management. The collection metadata systems manager is essentially owner of LMS.

Within the BL's front-end catalogue, descriptive metadata records are published for discovery. This assigns identifier to digital content via the metadata. This is a slightly different record, with certain fields hidden, or others added for accessibility, because it is the front end for users.

Within the BL systems, the metadata aggregator is supported by Technology, but the business owner is the Metadata team. The metadata aggregator is responsible for aggregating what comes out of the repository to support front end records in the front end catalogue, as well as linking content and metadata. The metadata aggregator takes data from multiple sources, including the LMS.

⁷ MARC is a means for the representation and communication of bibliographic information. MARC stands for MACHine-Readable Cataloging.

An output (of records) is made available via OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) to the legal deposit library for harvest.

The steps are usually completed in a chronological order, but some of the later steps can occur simultaneously.

5.3.7 Digital preservation

Processes such as checksums, and other data integrity checks, that are essential to preserve long term access to the digital book and metadata files are automated processes integral to the repository system.

Once the file package has moved through the preceding phases to the digital preservation phase it is replicated to two of the other five legal deposit libraries in the UK and Ireland. Currently this will be the National Library of Scotland and the National Library of Wales. The replication process is managed by Technology, but the business owner is Digital Preservation. For Digital Collection Management and Digital Preservation, the Technology team provides support functions (functions as a line running across processes in a support capacity). Within the broader workflow 'replication' is a standalone process, which means that there is scheduling flexibility for when it takes place.

5.3.8 Access

The discussion moved on to approach any access functions that were not yet captured. The question of takedown requests was raised, including any exception process.

There is a Notice and Takedown team at the BL, but the process is also agreed by the Legal Deposit libraries. The decision maker is the Publisher Communications Group (LDL). The team makes the decision whether to take down. But there is a technology process that does the actual process of removal.

The non-print legal deposit (NPLD) access system provides the opportunity to read any digital content collected under Legal Deposit, including open access content, but because of restrictions under the legislation the system may only be accessed on premises at the legal deposit libraries (and only one person can look at a specific book, article etc. at one time). This still applies to digital OA material due to the legislation that was based around access provision for printed materials. This has the same effect as if the item was made available under a single-use license (there is no license applied to legal deposit content). There is dedicated terminal access within the library reading rooms on LDL premises.

The BL catalogue is a single catalogue system that includes both content processed via other methods of acquisition (e.g. purchase or donation) as well as that ingested via Legal Deposit.

One participant mentioned a project undertaken at one point within the BL by the Discovery Services team. The project looked across multiple records with multiple access routes not to deduplicate records but add all access routes to the records for the same item. An action was taken to follow up the discussion with Discovery Services to gain more insight into this work, and how it can make use of records in DOAB (which are included in the knowledge base for Primo, the system used by the Library for its public catalogue).

The BL is investigating the ways in which readers might be able to see all versions of the same item without having to look at multiple records. The work is presently on hold as a consequence of the impacts of the cyber-attack but should be picking up after the new LMS is in place and may offer new opportunities in how access to content is provided.

5.4 Summary of Key Findings

The lack of an open access field in the predominant metadata standards used within the publishing, library and archiving domain makes maintaining the OA status of a book challenging for preservation purposes. The lack of an explicit OA field is further compounded by wide variation in the ways in which existing metadata standards are used. The implication of this finding is that when an OA book is digitally archived and preserved the digital preservation copy will not be available in the public domain, rather it will be dark archived alongside non-OA content.

6. Case Study II – Library and Archives Canada

6.1 Preamble

In 1950 the Canadian national bibliography, called *Canadiana*, was issued as a precursor to the National Library, with Legal Deposit being formally established with the *National Library of Canada Act* (1952). In 2004 the National Library of Canada then amalgamated with the National Archives of Canada under the *Library and Archives of Canada Act* (2004). Following this, the *National Library Book Deposit Regulations* (1995) were replaced by the *Legal Deposit of Publications Regulations* (2006), which came into effect in 2007 and included the first instructions for capturing digital publications.

This case study concerns the process for electronic deposit of digital publications under Canada's legal deposit regulations. Open access publications are recognised at Library and Archives Canada (LAC) as being publications where the publisher has indicated access does not need to be restricted under legal deposit. This is opposed to materials sent under restricted access and which can only be accessed on site at the library.

6.2 Participants

In the workshop participants represented teams and departments at LAC associated with legal deposit, metadata sharing, library standards development, library systems implementation, special collections, publishing industry monitoring and outreach, monograph description, and Cataloguing-in-Publication (CIP). These participants provided an overview of legal deposit workflows and the various touchpoints in the digital preservation lifecycle of an Open Access (OA) monograph. This conversation was also supplemented by further resources and materials provided outside of the workshop.

6.3 Findings

6.3.1 Phases and touchpoints

The same seven high level workflow phases relating to digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs which were identified in the focus group with the British Library, were also used in this conversation. This was intended as a means of comparing these workflows. These phases were:

1. Identify
2. Acquire

3. Pre-ingest
4. Ingest
5. Repository management
6. Digital preservation
7. Access

The touchpoints pertaining to these seven workflow phases involve a mix of internal and external stakeholders, such as units within LAC and publishers, but also automated systems and repositories. In contrast to the workflow phases, these touchpoints vary between each National Library. Figure 2 below illustrates these touchpoints in relation to the seven high level workflow phases, the process map can also be viewed in Appendix 2.

6.3.2 Identify

Under the *Library and Archives Canada Act* (2004), publishers are obliged to deposit publications to the LAC. Canadian publishers and producers are defined as being an entity that: publishes from an office/business in Canada; has at least 75% of its employees based in Canada; makes a publication or production available in Canada; and is authorized to reproduce publications / productions and control the content. Within this definition self-publishers are included if the author is a Canadian resident. In terms of open access publications, working papers and reports are also deposited from publishers based at Canadian Universities and other Canadian Institutions.

Many publishers actively deposit their publications with LAC. Where there are gaps, the Industry Monitoring team will identify publishers to reach out to. In addition to this there is a publisher outreach strategy which involves reaching out to diverse voices from indigenous publishers, LGBTQI+ publishers and other underrepresented communities to facilitate the legal deposit process, making sure people know where the website is and sending out the relevant information.

LAC administers a Cataloguing-in-Publication (CIP) program through which eligible Canadian publishers submit information about forthcoming publications using an online form. The CIP team creates a corresponding bibliographic record and data block; this data block, which is a summary of the bibliographic record, is then returned to the publisher for inclusion in the publication. As a result, a catalogue record may already exist at the time the publication is acquired.

LAC's pre-publication records for legal deposit acquisitions are used by the team to generate a message to publishers if they have not deposited after a certain amount of time. This message is called a 'claim'. Claims can also be generated for titles without a CIP record, when staff identify that a published title has not yet been received.

This represents the first element of non-linearity in LAC's workflow, as CIP records are also part of the pre-ingest workflow phase.

Figure 2

6.3.3 Acquisition

When submitting a single publication for legal deposit, the publisher will complete a webform to capture information and metadata, including declaring whether a publication is open access or restricted access. This webform and the information submitted, represent the permissions granted to LAC for access. As part of the webform for single titles, depositors also attach the publication files for upload.

Regarding the access status of monographs, it was clarified that the access status provided in the information received from the publisher is not generally questioned. However, it was mentioned that the Legal Deposit Acquisitions team will verify the access level if they notice the publication is available to purchase online on a site such as Amazon, but the form says it is open access; this is especially the case for self-publishers.

For publishers wanting to submit multiple publications they can send an excel spreadsheet containing the metadata records for all these submissions. The spreadsheet can also be used for submitting one title but is usually suggested if submitting more.

For publishers with ONIX metadata, metadata and assets are acquired through a separate workflow.

6.3.4 Pre-ingest

As part of the pre-ingest phase, form data, excel data, ONIX data and publication assets received from publishers are ingested into LAC's Digital Asset Transfer System GoAnywhere. GoAnywhere has submission workflows to transform the metadata, check for viruses, create checksums, and prepare ingest packages for the Preservica (LAC's digital preservation system) repository. All metadata is mapped to MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema) and preliminary MARC records are created.

In recent years, LAC has built an automated workflow to arrange incoming e-book / e-audiobook files with their ONIX metadata. Metadata crosswalks from ONIX (to MODS) to MARC, and automated enrichment with LAC-specific elements create the preliminary MARC records.

6.3.5 Ingest

After files and metadata have been transformed and checked through GoAnywhere, they are then ingested into LAC's Digital Preservation System Preservica.

6.3.6 Repository management

Once the monograph and its metadata record are in Preservica they are placed in the workspace area, where Acquisitions Technicians and Librarians perform manual checks. These checks include reviewing the metadata, whether the asset is in scope, and whether it is a duplicate. Once

these checks have been performed, the submission and its requisite parts are put into the appropriate space on Preservica.

If any changes need to be made to monographs following ingest, the record would be updated in OCLC library catalogue, whereas files can be replaced directly in Preservica.

Regarding takedown procedures and notices, participants mentioned that this is more common with theses and dissertations as opposed to legal deposit monographs. It was clarified that in these cases a tombstone record⁸ is not kept. If there was a takedown for an OA monograph, LAC would probably replace the assets, depending on the situation.

6.3.7 Digital preservation

Another non-linear aspect of LAC's workflow relates to their digital preservation. This is due to how the first touchpoint for OA monographs is the digital preservation platform Preservica, as opposed to being stored in a separate repository. In Preservica multiple copies are kept across multiple locations. Where required, Preservica does have a method of creating an access copy, however usually the copy received from the publisher is an ePub or PDF file so there is no need to create another copy because the functionality is built in.

At LAC there is an automated link between Preservica and the library catalogue Aurora (an implementation of OCLC WorldShare). Any digital publication record amended or created in the catalogue is synced back to Preservica. Although there is a copy of the catalogue record in Preservica, these records are not centrally managed through Preservica. The master copies of files deposited with LAC are kept in Preservica, whereas the master copies of metadata records are kept in *Aurora*. This also means that if any changes are made to the master copy of the record in Aurora, this is synced back to Preservica.

6.3.8 Access

The copy and records in Preservica represent the preservation copy, and if a monograph/digital asset is marked as open access within Preservica this will permit public access online through *Aurora*. This library catalogue links back to files in Preservica.

Records, publications and documents can also be accessed through LAC's online Collection search. Whilst Aurora represents LAC's catalogue of published material including print books, e-books, music, videos, magazines, maps and digital documents, Collection search represents both archival and published materials, including political, military and genealogy records. OA monographs and records can be accessed through both Aurora and Collection search.

⁸A tombstone record is a special marker in a database that indicates a record has been deleted, rather than physically removing the data immediately.

All monograph records and metadata are also available in OCLC Worldcat, a global online catalogue of library content.

At this stage in the discussion the OBF team queried whether LAC collects information on the specific licensing of monographs and digital assets; it was clarified that LAC does not collect licensing information.

6.4 Summary of Key Findings

A significant finding from LAC's workflow is that their Digital Preservation System Preservica serves several other complementary functions, including acting as the digital repository. In this context, the preservation copy is the access copy and can be accessed through both Aurora and Collection search. It is also significant that the 'pre-ingest' phase includes depositors completing an open access field, which allows for different processing in the early stages.

A noteworthy aspect of the workflow, in the 'pre-ingest' phase, is LAC's recently automated workflow to arrange incoming e-book / e-audiobook files with their ONIX metadata. As well as transforming from ONIX (to MODS) to MARC, there is also automated enrichment with LAC-specific elements that create the preliminary MARC records.

7. Case Study III – Qatar National Library

7.1 Preamble

Qatar National Library (QNL), established in 2018, serves three core roles: the National Library of Qatar, a public library for the community, and a research library supporting scholarship and innovation. It safeguards Qatar's documentary heritage through collecting, preservation, digitisation, and access. QNL holds over one million print books and more than 500,000 digital resources and provides access to heritage and research content through platforms such as the Qatar Digital Library, Manara (Qatar Research Repository), and QNL's Digital Repository.

Legal deposit legislation was first introduced in Qatar in 1982. Legal deposit is handled by another organisation, however authors and publishers may also deposit a copy with Qatar National Library if they choose.

7.2 Participants

The participants from the Qatar National Library were the Head of Open Access and Copyright, the Head of Digital Curation, Preservation and Access, and a representative from the Cataloguing and Metadata Team. Collectively these participants have oversight of the various touchpoints in the digital preservation lifecycle of OA monographs at Qatar National Library and the departments involved.

7.3 Findings

7.3.1 Phases and touchpoints

The same seven high level workflow phases relating to digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs which were identified in the first case study with the British Library, were used to start the discussion for this focus group. These phases were:

1. Identify
2. Acquire
3. Pre-ingest
4. Ingest
5. Repository management
6. Digital preservation
7. Access

The touchpoints pertaining to these seven workflow phases involve internal stakeholders, including units and automated systems and repositories within Qatar National Library. Figure 3 below illustrates these touchpoints in relation to the seven high level workflow phases. The absence of a legal deposit pipeline into Qatar National Library means that items are proactively sought via the collection policy since there is no formal process for publishers to ‘push’ content to the library. As a result, there are multiple processes by which OA monographs are digitally preserved by the Qatar National Library.

As monographs are identified via several different routes the following phases differ according to the route by which they are identified. This is represented in figure 3 by using a colour scheme to denote the different routes: Collections (green), Manara Research Repository (blue), and heritage materials in the Qatar Digital Library (yellow). Collections refers to OA monographs identified for the library catalogue, as opposed to those which go through Manara or the Qatar Digital Library.

Each of the seven workflow phases are discussed in turn below in relation to each of the three routes and their relevant touchpoints in the workflow process map shown in figure 3, the process map can also be viewed in Appendix 3.

7.3.2 Identify

There are several different ways that OA monographs are identified by Qatar National Library (QNL). One of these is through the existing collection, with work being carried out to identify OA monographs in the collection which are relevant to Qatar’s national heritage.

QNL also identifies OA monographs through an international aggregator of content ScienceOpen⁹, with whom the QNL has a partnership. ScienceOpen identifies OA monographs that qualify as being relevant to Qatar’s national heritage, this includes material that QNL may already have. To make such identifications ScienceOpen uses publicly available information, from open digital infrastructure organisations such as Cross Ref¹⁰ and identifies content through digital object identifiers (DOIs), checking that it is relevant to QNL. Although ScienceOpen performs these checks, there is sometimes information missing because it is completed through webpage scraping and crawling. Therefore, when material is received by QNL they check that the content is indeed relevant and double check the open access status. The relationship between QNL and ScienceOpen is reciprocal, and QNL has contributed metadata and records from Manara to ScienceOpen’s database as well as a recently published e-book with a DOI.

⁹ The webpages for ScienceOpen can be found here <https://www.scienceopen.com/>

¹⁰ The webpages for Cross Ref can be found here <https://www.crossref.org/>

Although QNL does not have a direct relationship with publishers, they have identified two Qatar-based university publishers, Qatar University Press and Hamad Bin Khalifa University Press, that do publish open access. They have been able to acquire these works as the monographs were accessible in the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)¹¹. QNL has also directly funded the publication of several OA monographs.

In the case of the Manara route described in this case study, OA monographs are directly deposited by Qatar-based researchers and universities. Participants discussed the fact that the wider goal is for institutions to have their own space and repositories within Manara to promote open access, not just through publishing but also through enabling preservation and good research data practices by using Manara. Another goal in the future would be to develop overlay publishing, so that authors and publishers who are not Qatar-based researchers or institutions could also directly deposit their work in Manara.

For the heritage materials made available through the Qatar Digital Library (QDL), content is identified and developed through Qatar National Library's wider digital repatriation programme, which works with international partner institutions to select, digitise, curate, preserve, and provide access to heritage collections relating to Qatar and the Gulf region. One of the programme's foundational partnerships—between Qatar Foundation, Qatar National Library, and the British Library—launched QDL in 2014 as a bilingual, open-access digital archive. The repatriated content made accessible through QDL includes reports, letters, manuscripts, photographs, maps, drawings, and sound recordings.

As the discussion evolved, participants raised concerns about identifying OA monographs published in Arabic. This concern arose when discussing the international library systems and repositories used by QNL, which are based on the English-language by default. For instance, whilst the online repository system Figshare¹², which is the external system used to support Manara, does allow Arabic text and register-transfer language (RTL) in some fields, it does not natively support Arabic and is not optimal for QNL's needs. Participants also discussed how Arabic publications are sometimes published without a DOI, will often not be available from sources such as Google Scholar,¹³ will often not have effectively structured metadata, and will be difficult to search for using aggregators of Arabic publications. This raised the question of where Arabic publications should be located and how these challenges in preservation can be overcome.

¹¹ The webpages for the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) can be found here <https://www.doabooks.org/>

¹² The webpages for Figshare can be found here <https://figshare.com/>

¹³ The webpages for Google Scholar can be found here <https://scholar.google.com/>

Figure 3

7.3.3 Acquisition

In the case of OA monographs identified for QNL's collections, these are acquired through the decision of whether they qualify as being relevant to Qatar's national heritage and whether they are openly available to be acquired. This decision is similar for materials identified as part of Qatar Digital Library's wider repatriation programme.

In the case of the Manara Research Repository, OA monographs need to have an author affiliation with a Qatar-based institution which will qualify whether it goes to Manara. For edited volumes, the editor or some of the authors need to be Qatar-based.

When individual authors deposit on Manara, they agree to the terms and conditions of service and choose a licence when uploading individual monographs. When institutions deposit on behalf of authors, they fill in a licencing form which gives approval for materials uploaded to Manara to be under a Creative Commons licence. Agreeing to the terms and conditions of service allows QNL to preserve the content, as well as making it open access.

7.3.4 Pre-ingest

At the pre-ingest phase, there are several different ways that metadata is captured. In the process map the main touchpoint has been described as ‘Cataloguing (several teams involved)’ as all three teams represented by the participants were involved in some capacity in reviewing and creating metadata records both at the pre-ingest phase and the ingest phase.

In the case of OA monographs identified by QNL for their collections, a metadata record is imported from the Online Computer Library Center (OCLC)¹⁴ where available. During the focus group, participants raised the issue that it is often unclear from OCLC records whether a monograph is open access and some monographs have previously been deposited without a metadata record. It was also noted that if the metadata has originated from OCLC, rather than from within QNL, the level of openness will vary.

For OA monographs added to the library catalogue, metadata records are created in Sierra using MARC format as the primary cataloguing standard. For items identified through the Qatar Digital Library Repatriation Programme, metadata is created within the QDL workflow, and not in the library catalogue (Sierra). These two processes are separate, and metadata creation does not take place in a single unified system.

7.3.5 Ingest

At the Ingest phase, for OA monographs identified for the collection, a master copy is created in Sierra. It was noted that anything that goes through Manara does not go into Sierra. Therefore, for OA monographs in Manara, the ingest phase is synonymous with the identify phase, as authors and institutions directly deposit their items into the repository. Similarly, monographs identified through Qatar Digital Library’s wider repatriation programme are not catalogued in Sierra.

¹⁴ The webpages for the Online Computer Library Centre (OCLC) can be found here <https://www.oclc.org/en/home.html>

After OA monographs that are registered in the collection registry are assigned an identifier, they are sent to a digital data warehouse. In the digital data warehouse pre-ingest records are imported in MARC format, which is then normalised to a Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) record and metadata enhancements are added by the metadata team. The MODS record allows the team to identify where the access copy or master copy is and see the relationship between these two copies. Metadata that is created by QNL for items in their catalogue, is openly viewable in the library catalogue.

For OA monographs deposited into Manara, QNL retrieves the metadata and files via the Figshare application programming interface (API), a set of protocols that enable different software components to communicate and transfer data and processes them through an automated pipeline. As part of this workflow, QNL packages each deposited item as an Oxford Common File Layout (OCFL) object for preservation and then reviews and transforms the descriptive metadata into a MODS record. Focus group participants noted that because Manara supports multiple content types (including research datasets), the platform-generated metadata is not always sufficiently aligned to OA monographs and may require refinement. In Manara, the metadata record is published openly alongside the item.

7.3.6 Repository management

QNL's catalogue is managed in Sierra, whereas Manara uses a Figshare repository. As a new repository is being developed, a MARC to MODS mapping is being maintained to ensure that Sierra records can be ingested into the new repository as it is developed. During the repository management phase, a preservation copy is created for all digital OA monographs from the three different identification routes.

In terms of repository management, during the focus group it was questioned whether QNL had a process of removing material from the repository and whether they had take down notices. It was noted that there has been no use case to date for OA monographs in Manara. In Qatar Digital Library there has been some restricted access due to copyright, for which there is an automated process which automatically suppresses images when the licencing changes. The participants also noted that although there is a process for OA monograph retractions, there have been no retractions yet.

7.3.7 Digital preservation

QNL's long-term digital preservation service for open access content is built on an Archivematica-based preservation solution, implemented in 2020 alongside the library's wider Azure storage and backup infrastructure.

For OA monographs deposited in Manara, QNL retrieves content and metadata via the Figshare/Manara API. As previously indicated in the ‘Ingest’ phase, the retrieved outputs are processed through automated pipelines that normalize them into OCFL packages. These are then ingested into the QNL digital repository. Within the repository, preservation actions—including technical characterization and, where required, format migration—are driven by a detailed, actionable file format policy that specifies what should be preserved as-is, normalized, or migrated, and under what conditions.

Participants clarified that QNL actively tries to increase awareness around digital preservation, through their work with the Digital Preservation Coalition and in their position as a National Library.

7.3.8 Access

For each different identification route into QNL there is a different access route. For both Manara and the Qatar Digital Library, OA monographs and items are accessed directly through each of these digital systems. OA monographs that are identified via the National Collections Department, however, are available through the Library Catalogue (Sierra). Some of the OA monographs in Sierra are also available as print copies in the QNL holdings.

In the discussion the participants from QNL said that although there are currently three different entry points for accessing digital OA monographs, the goal would be to include all areas on the same platform. However, they also specified that Manara would continue to be a stand-alone repository, and that the more immediate goal is to adopt a single search engine from which OA monographs can be searched and accessed.

7.4 Summary of Key Findings

As there are three different ways in which OA monographs are identified and collected at QNL, there are three different workflows for their collections, the Manara research repository and for the Qatar Digital Library. These findings therefore provide a useful overview of three different types of digital preservation workflows, as well as the types of publishers and collections that are producing or consist of OA monographs. This focus on open access at QNL also means that there is a good overview of the differences between metadata and licencing depending on which route these publications come through.

8. Case Study IV – The National Library of Scotland

8.1 Preamble

The National Library was established formally by an Act of Parliament in 1925 in Scotland. Before that there was the Library of the Faculty of Advocates which played a role in collecting and preserving knowledge and was entitled to claim a copy of every book published in Britain following the Copyright Act of 1710. This formed the basis for the National Library of Scotland's role in legal deposit.

The National Library of Scotland (NLS) is one of the six legal deposit libraries in the United Kingdom and Ireland that receive a copy of all UK and Irish print publications and share access to the electronic content that is deposited. The others being The British Library, The National Library of Wales, Trinity College in Dublin, Cambridge University Library and the Bodleian Library in Oxford.

The National Library of Scotland also receives digital deposits directly from Scottish publishers and organisations, to collect and digitally preserve Scottish digital publications. These digital publications are the focus of this case study.

8.2 Participants

The participants from the National Library of Scotland were the Acquisitions Manager, a Senior Legal Deposit Librarian, the Head of Metadata and the Digital Preservation Manager.

8.3 Findings

8.3.1 Phases and touchpoints

The same seven high level workflow phases relating to digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs which were identified in the first case study with the British Library, were used to start the discussion for this focus group. These phases were:

1. Identify
2. Acquire
3. Pre-ingest
4. Ingest
5. Repository management
6. Digital preservation

7. Access

The touchpoints pertaining to these seven workflow phases involve internal stakeholders, including units and automated systems and repositories within The National Library of Scotland (NLS). Notably, due to the relationship NLS has with the British Library as one of the legal deposit libraries in the UK and Ireland, the British Library is represented as a touchpoint.

Figure 4 below illustrates these touchpoints in relation to the seven high level workflow phases. The process map can also be viewed in Appendix 4.

8.3.2 Identify

The scope of works identified for preservation by The National Library of Scotland are monographs available digitally and published by Scottish publishers. This includes materials and monographs published more generally by organisations in Scotland, such as Charities and Government bodies, whose material is often open access. Curators from the Published Collections team will also discuss to decide what is in scope and identify works. As a legal deposit library in the UK and Ireland, NLS also has materials highlighted to them via the British Library.

The Acquisitions team receive individual enquiries about legal deposit from publishers. As well as these enquiries, the Acquisitions team reach out by phone and email to individual publishers in Scotland to describe the legal deposit process. This conversation is often the starting point and identifies whether a digital publication is within scope to be digitally deposited at NLS. This conversation between the Acquisitions team and publishers, including Scottish organisations publishing materials and monographs, also covers several of the other phases in the workflow and therefore is not an action only associated with identifying a monograph.

8.3.3 Acquisition

Once it is determined that the publisher is Scottish and within scope, then publishers are set up with digital deposit by the Acquisitions team.

As publishers are also identified through direct queries to the Acquisitions team, or by the Acquisitions team approaching them, this acquisition also covers pre-ingest information rather than just determining whether monographs are in scope. Participants mentioned that this is a conversation that is often revisited by the Acquisitions team, due to factors such as staff turnover at publishing organisations.

An aspect of acquisition that was mentioned later in the conversation regarding preservation, was creating a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between NLS and depositing organisations that permits the materials to be preserved and outlines access conditions. However, it was clarified that this was only the case for a few organisations, such as the Scottish Government,

and was not generally the case for most publishers depositing materials. For most non-commercial publishers depositing at a smaller scale, any agreement on access conditions, which are generally unrestricted, is kept in the Library Management System vendor records.

8.3.4 Pre-ingest

Before the ingest phase of the workflow, the Acquisitions team uses a template of questions to aid publishers in digitally depositing their files. This stage is chronologically in the acquisition phase of the workflow, as it is often part of the initial conversations the Acquisitions team have with publishers, however the conversation is also inclusive of the pre-ingest phase as information is collected in relation to ingest, preservation and access.

Publishers can either deposit using Digital Deposit Scotland or through a Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP). Digital Deposit Scotland is an online service which publishers can use to upload their electronic publications. Before publishers can deposit their materials, the Acquisitions team set up an account for them and an automated email is sent to the publisher so they can log in. Publishers cannot set up their own accounts. In cases of larger file transfers, a SFTP is provided to secure file transfer over a data stream, enabling transfers of large files, as well as enabling files to be encrypted.

The questions asked by the Acquisitions team are adapted for each publisher, depending on their requirements but usually cover what file type the publisher has, whether they will use SFTP rather than Digital Deposit Scotland – as is the case for larger publishers, and what email will be used to setup their Digital Deposit Scotland and for ongoing contact. In this conversation publishers are encouraged to use particular file names and formats to aid ingest, preservation and access.

UK Legal Deposit legislation requires that, regardless of whether publications are open access, those deposited under legal deposit terms can only be read from within the library reading rooms, and not remotely from home. Therefore, in the initial conversations the Acquisitions team has with publishers, they ask if they would be willing to grant access so monographs can be read remotely, from outside of the library's reading rooms. As opposed to open access, this is called wider access. Wider access is generally set at publisher level, rather than on an individual deposit basis.

8.3.5 Ingest

Once publishers have an account, they can deposit materials directly to Digital Deposit Scotland. For larger publishers making multiple deposits at any one time, they use a SFTP, as discussed in the pre-ingest phase. The materials deposited are then sent to a cloud server where security

Figure 14

checks are automatically performed, and where the IT team can perform additional checks if necessary, before they are permitted to come on to the internal system at NLS. Once security checks have been performed, the files deposited are sent to an internal server and information about these deposits is sent to an internal dashboard, which is then accessed by the wider team at NLS. On the dashboard the Acquisitions team can set the access type, both regarding whether the publisher has agreed to wider access and regarding legal deposit access terms. This

information about access type also determines where the files are stored in order to facilitate the different access levels.

As well as being recorded on the dashboard, materials which have been checked also move from the cloud server to NLS drives. This sends an automated email to the Acquisitions team. This also triggers an automated process which gives deposited materials a PID number, a persistent identifier which acts as the internal identifier, as well as an XML template for metadata which includes a 245 field pulled from the file name and publication details, as well as an 856 URL field.

Participants discussed how prior to 2024 quite a few stages in the process were manual, including giving a PID and creating an XML template as well as moving files manually. Since then, these parts of the process have been updated to be automated.

A partial record, referred to as a stub record, is then automatically created from XML template in ALMA, NLS's Library Management System. The stub record description is then enhanced programmatically to update publisher details and corporate body names where available. The stub record is visible in the public catalogue (Primo) from this point in the process. This record stays in ALMA as a stub record until a cataloguer then upgrades the record, upgrading the record is manual in this instance to make records richer – as the catalogues represent Scottish publications the upgrades to the records include the addition of Library of Congress Subjects Headings, FAST Headings and Library of Congress Name Authority Headings for creators associated with the publication.

During this part of the discussion, it was queried whether the metadata reflects that a monograph is open access. Participants clarified that metadata currently does not distinguish whether a monograph is open access and the library does not embed Creative Commons licence information in the metadata they produce. This information would only be visible to users when accessing the published PDF. However, NLS do add an internal 'OA' code to records not visible to the public to indicate the work described is open access. As NLS discussed, currently they collect few OA publishers, but this internal code recognises that they may collect more, and this code will be useful if NLS decides to present OA content in a different way in the future. It was also clarified that whilst NLS generated metadata is available under a Creative Commons licence, metadata that has been purchased, e.g. via WorldCat, will not be made available under a Creative Commons licence.

As the publications deposited are local to Scotland, it is unlikely there will be an existing catalogue record with the metadata, therefore as well as sending ALMA records to the British Library for legal deposit, the Metadata Team will also send them to online catalogues such as WorldCat and JISC Library Hub.

When sending metadata records to the British Library for legal deposit, the Metadata team extract a METs file. This metadata file, and access to the PDFs, are shared with the other Legal Deposit Libraries. For NLS this process results in two metadata records in Alma. One metadata record provides wider access via the NLS catalogue so that readers can access these publications from home. The other legal deposit record can only be accessed from within library reading rooms and this latter version is the only version the British Library and other Legal Deposit Libraries have.

8.3.6 Repository management

In terms of a repository, participants suggested that NLS's Digital Preservation system could be considered as the repository, as this system takes in the original files. In the Digital Preservation system there is another METs metadata file, separate from the METs file sent to the British Library, which includes bibliographic and access information.

Regarding repository management, it was questioned whether there are takedown policies and takedown notices for OA monographs at NLS. Takedowns are handled on a case-by-case basis at NLS, who have a shared Noticed and Takedown policy with the other Legal Deposit Libraries as well as a shared discussion and procedure for each case.

In the case of NLS, if takedown is agreed then the necessary action is taken on the dashboard and on Alma, which may be an action such as suppressing access to the title in question.

For a monograph and its record to be taken down there needs to be a very strong and likely legal justification, such as a court injunction, legal requirements, proven violations of copyright or database right not covered by legal deposit legislation or a limitation or exception in UK copyright law, material that has been found to be libellous or defamatory and breaches of confidentiality. This decision is guided by policy, and when agreed the record is suppressed, but a suppressed archive copy is kept. However, it was noted that cases of locally ingested materials being taken down were rare.

On the issue of taking down materials, NLS also discussed that it is important that a footprint of the catalogue remains, for both NLS's auditing and understanding. Therefore, part of the takedown policy is focussed on maintaining an ongoing record of collection, whilst complying with any formal decision or legal instruction to remove public access to the title in question.

8.3.7 Digital preservation

Several digital preservation steps are included as part of the ingest phase. For instance, the METs metadata record in NLS's Digital Preservation system includes the actions which can be taken with a file in terms of preservation. In the METs record events are recorded, creating an auditable history of the monograph within the NLS.

At the ingest phase, the PID (persistent identifier) record is assigned in NLS's in-house preservation system. Further on in the workflow this record is embellished within the preservation system, including checksums for preservation.

The Preservation team then creates three copies which are kept in three different storage locations. Every year the Preservation team checks two of these copies to make sure that the files are still as they were when they were originally deposited.

Participants also discussed that there is a process to retrospectively preserve records that have already gone through the system, using the same process for ongoing acquisitions at NLS.

8.3.8 Access

Wider access files and records are directly accessible through NLS's front facing main catalogue system.

Therefore, there are two routes to accessing wider access publications and two records, either online through NLS's main catalogue, or through reading room legal deposit access at sites such as the British Library or any of the other legal deposit libraries in the UK.

8.4 Summary of Key Findings

As the electronic deposit digital preservation workflow for Scottish digital publications is in part additional to NLS's role as a UK legal deposit library, there are several notable findings that can be related to this. A point that has been emphasised is the large role of outreach and education that the Acquisitions team performs in the initial phases of 'identify', 'acquisition' and 'pre-ingest', although this is often due to gaps in publisher awareness. It also presents an opportunity for impacting the formats and information received from publishers. Another noteworthy finding is that NLS uses the term 'wider access' in place of open access, perhaps as a way of making the distinction between the access provided by NLS for these publications and that provided by UK legal deposit libraries. 'Wider access' is conceptually the same as Gratis open access, as opposed to Libre open access, meaning that monographs can be openly viewed but not necessarily openly reused and reproduced.

9. Case Study V – National Library of the Czech Republic

9.1 Preamble

Legal deposit was established in the Czech Republic in 1782, following the establishment of Public Imperial and Royal University Library in 1777, when the library acquired the right to legal deposit of every book published by Prague printers and publishers. In 1807 this extended to include the entire territory of the Kingdom of Bohemia and, in 1812, to newspapers, magazines, and maps.

The Public and University Library in Czechoslovakia was established in 1917 and renamed the National and University Library in 1935, when the National Library gained a permanent conservation role for legal deposit. The library was re-named the National Library of the Czech Republic (NLCR) in 1990.

Legal deposit in the Czech Republic is governed by two laws, the Non-Periodical Publications Act and the Press Act. Legislative proposals to include electronic legal deposit for non-periodical publications assigned eISBNs and periodicals with assigned eISSNs have been presented in the Chamber of Deputies of the Czech Republic in 2012, 2016, 2019 and 2023. At the time of writing, the proposal is going through parliamentary processes.

This case study describes the current voluntary process for electronic deposits, which has been developed at the library in preparation for the legislation change, with a view of understanding the considerations required for these types of deposits, as well as how this would impact OA monographs.

At the beginning of the discussion the definition of open access on the Open Book Futures was queried. Participants clarified that in the Czech Republic there is a law defining open access, the Act on the Support of Research and Development with Public Funds (Act on the Support of Research and Development), but NLCR works with various other Acts when determining access of their digital documents. This means that in the case of an OA monograph at NLCR, this will be mostly defined by its being freely and publicly available.

9.2 Participants

The participants from the National Library of the Czech Republic were the Director of Modern Digital Collections, the Head of Digital Document Management and Archiving, the Head of the Digital Preservation Standards Department and a Metadata Analyst

9.3 Findings

9.3.1 Phases and touchpoints

The same seven high level workflow phases relating to digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs which were identified in the first case study with the British Library, were used to start the discussion for this focus group, though the chronology of these phases varied. These phases were:

1. Identify
2. Acquire
3. Pre-ingest
4. Ingest
5. Repository management
6. Digital preservation
7. Access

The touchpoints pertaining to these seven workflow phases involve internal stakeholders, including units, automated systems and repositories within The National Library of the Czech Republic.

Figure 5 below illustrates these touchpoints in relation to the seven high level workflow phases. The process map can also be viewed in Appendix 5.

9.3.2 Identify

The scope of works identified for preservation by The National Library of the Czech Republic are books and monographs published either with a Czech author, published in Czech, or on a topic related to the Czech Republic (regardless of whether the author is Czech or which country the book or monograph is published in). The types of organisations producing publications that the library work with range from regional special interest groups to larger national and international commercial publishers.

It was clarified by participants that although some content is harvested from the Web based

domain name for the Czech Republic (.cz) for web archiving purposes, this is a separate process from how materials are identified for legal deposit and electronic deposit.

As electronic deposit is currently voluntary in the Czech Republic, digital monographs are mostly identified through the Department of Acquisitions contacting publishers to make them aware that electronic deposit is possible. Given that electronic publications are not currently included under legal deposit, the Department of Acquisitions team have an educational role in explaining to publishers the advantages of electronic deposit and digitally preserving their materials in this way.

9.3.3 Acquisition

For publishers to electronically deposit monographs, they must first sign an Agreement with NLCR. The agreement states the formats in which NLCR can receive electronic deposits, including PDF/A, PDF/A 1a, PDF/A 1b, PDF/A 2a, PDF/A 2b, PDF/A 2u and EPUB 2.0.1. It also states what NLCR can do with the works received, including digital preservation and access. Participants also discussed how they will be suggesting that details of these file formats should be included in a supplement to the act to include electronic legal deposit. However, as the inclusion of this in legislation cannot be guaranteed, NLCR are focussed on the ways in which they can educate publishers ahead of time about formats and other ways in which they can support publishers with file conversion, which is detailed further on in the workflow.

Currently information on the file formats required for digital preservation and details on how electronic materials are preserved is sent to publishers in the first instance. These requirements are included on NLCR's website in handbooks for monographs, periodicals, sound documents etc. on the definition of metadata formats for digitisation.

9.3.4 Pre-ingest

At the pre-ingest phase, the Department of Acquisition receives information from the publisher via a webform in the electronic submission system where publishers fill in information about the title and access. Publishers require a log in to access the electronic submission system, for which they need to be registered.

This information automatically produces a catalogue and metadata record, which is later enhanced in the ingest phase of the workflow, and against which the details in the electronic document received can be checked.

Figure 5

9.3.5 Ingest

Once the agreement has been received, the publisher will then deposit digital files in NLCR's in-house electronic submission system, after providing the required information in the webform. Currently, it is only possible to upload one publication at a time. Participants did acknowledge that publishers will require the means of submitting multiple publications and are preparing for that request.

Participants discussed how despite recommendations of which file types are best for digital preservation being sent to publishers ahead of ingest, that publishers still tend to deposit PDF files, as this is what they receive themselves from authors. At the time of writing, the National Library of the Czech Republic converts these files to PDF/A upon receiving them. They have however developed a conversion tool, which is currently being tested internally, which publishers will be able to use when depositing digital documents in the submission system.

If there is an existing ISBN, when the file is deposited, the Department of ISBN will download information from ALEPH, NLCR's library catalogue and database, for the cataloguing and metadata records. If there is no existing ISBN, cataloguing and metadata records will have been automatically created using the information supplied by the publisher.

Before these records are enriched, NLCR has a processing workflow, in which several teams are involved. This processing workflow involves the Department of Acquisition, the Department of the ISBN, and the Department of Cataloguing. As well as checking the files are accessible and preservable and that the information provided is correct, this is also when electronic deposits are given their persistent identifier, a long-lasting reference to the digital object.

After this processing workflow, the Department of Post-Processing will transform the metadata and enhance the records. Participants clarified however, that in the cases where there is an existing ISBN and catalogue record, this is not verified against the metadata and the digital package, meaning that if the catalogue record is incorrect but the metadata record is accurate, they will accept the data package.

Following the ingest phase, digital publications and their records are sent to NLCR's long-term preservation (LTP) system.

9.3.6 Repository management

NLCR's library system ALEPH connects to the electronic submission system, the long-term preservation system and the Digital Library. This means that changes made in ALEPH are synced to these three systems.

Regarding NLCR's takedown procedures, participants clarified that this only happens in the Digital Library, where OA monographs are made available online. Publications are not deleted, rather the licence is changed, and a catalogue record will exist, but it is not available for wider reading. This is because the Digital Library also works as a catalogue of digitised books, as well as an access point for openly accessible publications.

In these cases, the publication will be made private and only accessible to users on library premises, in accordance with legislation.

9.3.7 Digital preservation

The digital preservation phase of the workflow at NLCR begins as soon as a monograph is identified, as at this stage information on the file types and information required for digital preservation is sent to publishers. This information is then included in the agreement publishers sign in the acquisition phase and is processed and checked at the ingest phase.

After digital publications are received in NLCR's custom built LTP system, metadata is enhanced for use in the Digital Library where openly accessible publications can be accessed. These enhancements therefore are for searching purposes and otherwise the data is kept the same.

There are two versions kept of digital files in the data package received. One of these versions is in maximum resolution and of the higher quality which is used for archival purposes only and is dark archived. The other version is a lower resolution or is a compressed file format and is for viewing purposes in the Digital Library, which is less demanding on the system and means users can access files more quickly.

For preservation purposes, three copies of digital publications are kept on magnetic tapes. One of these is an online copy, another is an offline copy and one copy of the three is also geographically distanced.

9.3.8 Access

If they are publicly available, electronically deposited OA monographs may be accessed via the Digital Library, which is on an open-source system. When a digital publication is not open access or creative commons, this can only be accessed on a terminal on library premises. In these cases, NLCR will receive one copy, and it can only be viewed by one person at a time.

Previously monographs were either set as public or private, whereas in a newer version of the

Digital Library it will be possible for monographs set to public access to be set as open access, distinguishing between different licences.

Participants also gave an example of one magazine which now publishes all its articles under a Creative Commons licence, and therefore NLCR were asked to publish under this licence in the Digital Library.

9.4 Summary of Key Findings

Notably, as electronic legal deposit legislation has not yet been passed in The Czech Republic, a lot of NLCR's focus is on establishing mechanisms for deposit, as well as developing and refining these mechanisms. This is evident in their proposals for the inclusion of optimum file formats for digital preservation in agreements and legislation, as well as developing their ingest mechanism to include a PDF to PDF/A file converter. This means that as well as being receptive to learnings from the shared practice of other National Libraries, NLCR also has developed practice that is worth sharing.

10. Discussion

In this discussion chapter the main findings from the case studies will be analysed in relation to the challenges associated with the long-term digital preservation of OA legal deposit monographs and the opportunities presented for an international National Libraries network for open access and digital preservation. These findings and discussion points are mostly focussed on implications for National Libraries, however there is some indication of the implications for publishers and the wider digital preservation community.

10.1 Open Access Definitions, Metadata, Licencing and Awareness

In conversations with the participating National Libraries involved in this research, there was a variation in the technical and cultural definitions of open access. There are two components of open access, that of online access to research literature being free of charge, and free of most usage restrictions, signified in Suber's (2008) use of terms 'Gratis Open Access' and 'Libre Open Access' (p.12 of this report). Participants were more focussed on free of charge online access. This focus often means that open access is referred to in slightly different terms than open access in communications with publishers and how these monographs are labelled when accessed online, with examples including 'Wider Access' (p. 39 of this report) and 'freely and publicly accessible' (p. 45 of this report). Whilst National Libraries use the term open access or another term in their internal processes it is not necessarily significant for the preservation of this status, but it does emphasise more of a focus on monographs being openly available as opposed to also being free of usage restrictions.

What is more significant for the preservation of a monograph's open access status is that the term is used consistently within the library metadata. In several of the case studies metadata collected and created by participants did not represent whether a publication is open access, either because there is no field to record this, it had not been included in pre-existing metadata records or due to incomplete information received from publishers. This suggests a risk to the long-term preservation of the open access status of OA monographs, as although the publication files may be digitally preserved and accessible, the recording of this status in metadata is not. This suggests the need for the inclusion of open access in national and international metadata standards as a recommendation for policy, in the interest of preserving the open access status of a publication.

Although in most of the case studies OA monographs can be accessed through front facing online catalogues, notably in one case OA monographs can only be accessed on site on digital terminals. This represents another point at which OA monographs are at risk of losing their open access

status and quality in the digital preservation process, as in this case they cannot be accessed freely or be reused. Again, this suggests another recommendation for policy, stipulating that open access works legally deposited to National Libraries should be available online.

When considering monographs that are free of usage restrictions, licencing and recording licences such as Creative Commons licences are a crucial aspect of preserving the open access status of these publications (p. 12 of this report). Amongst the participating libraries, several did not have a current mechanism for recording these licences or were not receiving such information from publishers. These variations between definitions and licencing suggest a risk to the preservation of the open access status of OA monographs as well as the potential for different definitions to be applied to the same works. As well as this risk to the preservation of open access status, when licencing is not openly and obviously displayed, the onus is on the user to find and abide by the relevant copyright. Fields recording reuse permissions of the work therefore should be included in the metadata stored by the NL and made publicly available. Despite the risk to open access status identified here, it should also be noted that several participants did state that they are working towards the inclusion of different licences in their documentation and systems.

A possible reason for these variations in definitions of open access and these aspects not being consistently recorded through licencing, is that currently within the scope of both legal deposit and the majority of National Libraries' collections policies, open access materials represent a relatively small proportion of items that they handle. The findings in this research suggest that, for National Libraries that do not handle legal deposit, there is a stronger focus on open access. This is evidenced in the Qatar National Library case study, which operates the Manara research repository and has in some cases funded the publication of open access monographs. This suggests that the scope of collection policies and the staff resource required for legal deposit could both potentially have a detrimental impact on the preservation of open access status. Although several participants did not currently have the mechanisms to preserve open access licencing and status, the fact that several are working to include this in their future processes suggests that outreach to publishers, both in terms of expanding collections to include more open access works but also in increasing awareness about the different types of access and licencing that can be recorded, could play an important role in the digital preservation of OA monographs.

10.2 The Steps Before Ingest

Early in the OA monograph preservation workflow workshops, it was identified that there are several stages before 'ingest' in the preservation workflow (p. 19 of this report). In all the case studies these pre-ingest phases are critical in shaping digital preservation and access outcomes. These phases involve several teams and systems, including digital preservation departments, in the collection of relevant information from publishers. Significantly, in several cases information

collected from the publisher in these initial stages informs the creation of metadata as well as the access status and requirements of publications, before the files for publication are ingested. Furthermore, information provided to publishers, both as part of identifying monographs and as part of acquiring monographs, has an impact on preservation. For instance, in several cases the file formats best suited for preservation, such as PDF and PDF/A, are recommended or stipulated before 'ingest', using information from Digital Preservation departments. In one case study, conversations are being held regarding the possibility of including preservable file formats as part of both electronic legal deposit legislation and the agreements made between the publisher and the National Library (p. 47 of this report). This example of including preservable file formats in legislation and agreements, as a way of educating publishers and policy makers on what is required for effective digital preservation, is something that could be replicated for open access licencing. These examples suggest that there is potential for also including open access terminology and information about licences in the earlier stages before 'ingest'.

The inclusion of information on digital preservation in the phases before 'ingest' in the workflow emphasises not just the importance of these phases but also the success of a 'preservation by design' approach. Integrating cataloguing and preservation in the earlier phases, as opposed to digital preservation being handled as a separate process in the later workflow phases, ensures best practice for digital preservation and a consistency amongst preserved materials.

From these findings, and through analysis of the touchpoints in the workflow process maps, it is clear that the workflow phases before 'ingest' signify the point at which National Libraries are communicating in the most direct way with publishers and depositors. Several of the participants were involved in the voluntary deposit of digital materials, for reasons such as legal deposit being handled by external organisations, electronic legal deposit not being formally legislated and to expand collections identified as in scope beyond traditional legal deposit. Particularly, but not exclusively, in these cases the 'identify' phase of the workflow takes on a new importance. Identifying materials often also involves education and promoting awareness of either existing legal deposit legislation, opportunities to deposit materials and best practice for ensuring digital preservation of these materials. The fact that the 'identify' phase is also significant in non-voluntary legal deposit, also suggests a gap in knowledge on legal deposit legislation and digital preservation in publishers generally, particularly amongst smaller publishers and presses. This lack of awareness also raises the question of how OA Monographs are being specifically identified for legal deposit, and what outreach and education may be needed in these cases. These phases also present an opportunity for specific outreach to smaller open access publishers, and the inclusion of open access information in these initial conversations with publishers.

As the phases before ingest are often the least technically demanding and least dependent on specific systems and resources, they arguably represent the greatest opportunity for what could be achieved through a National Libraries network on open access and digital preservation, as

these conversations and information are elements that could be more easily modelled by, and replicated by, libraries.

10.3 Preservation by Design

As indicated in the previous section on ‘The Steps Before Ingest’ the participants in this research can be described as taking a ‘preservation by design’ approach to the digital preservation of OA monographs. As well as this being evident in information about digital preservation being included in the initial phases of the workflow, it is also conspicuous in further decisions and processes in several of the participant’s workflows. For instance, several of the National Libraries we spoke to indicated that their Digital Preservation system also represented their digital repository, as opposed to these being separate systems (p. 29 & p. 43 of this report). There was a variation between whether these systems were custom built internal systems or externally provided solutions. Whilst the reasoning for this could be argued to be in the interest of rationalising systems and resources, and that one system is easier to manage depending on national context, it still suggests that these participants are placing digital preservation practices at the forefront of their workflow.

In addition to there being cases where the digital preservation system is also the repository system, there were also instances amongst the participating National Libraries where the preservation copy of a publication file is also the access copy (p.29 of this report). This practice reflects the Copim Open Archiving principles identified by work package 7 on the Open Book Futures project (Cole, Gatti and Mitcham 2026). These practices suggest the potential for Open Archiving principles to be adopted more widely by National Libraries. In particular, the notion of having a mechanism for the open display and download of approved content. Further discussion of these principles could form part of the activities of a National Libraries network.

Regarding take down procedures and notices, although several participants indicated that there had been few cases in their particular context, the majority of participants said that they would not completely delete records, emphasising the importance of keeping a record of activity. For example, where there is an access copy, in addition to a preservation copy, then the access copy is removed, but the preservation copy is retained (p. 29, p. 43, p. 50 of this report). In this way National Libraries are adopting clear and transparent policies for takedown processes which is part of the Copim Open Archiving Criteria. This again implies the value of an opportunity for a network of National Libraries to discuss how take down procedures and notices affect open access works and the potential of Open Archiving principles being utilised in differing contexts.

10.4 Information sharing in practices, definitions and experiences

At the 'ingest' phase of the workflow there were variations between whether there were manual or automated processes in place, which has a significant impact on staff resource and the number of touchpoints required. In several of these cases automated processes had either recently been implemented, or there were plans to automate processes that are currently manual. Notable examples include an existing automated workflow to arrange incoming e-book/e-audiobook files with their ONIX metadata and the plans for an automated process for publishers to convert PDF files to PDF/A when depositing their files. Both these instances, as well as further examples in the case studies, represent the potential for digital preservation practice that could be shared in a National Libraries network. As well as demonstrating best practice for digital preservation, these examples also demonstrate steps that can be taken to relieve some of the pressure on staff resource.

Documenting digital preservation practices at National Libraries through the process mapping workshops proved useful for identifying successes, challenges and areas for improvement in the context of this research but also as a way of National Libraries clarifying their own processes. Based on the methodology used here, there is potential for further National Libraries to undertake this analysis themselves, an activity in which would be aided by the resources in this report, but also in further discussions in a National Libraries network.

11. Policy Recommendations

As part of the work package Archiving and Digital Preservation on the Open Book Futures project, policy recommendations for national and international policy makers have been developed in the areas of National Libraries Digital Preservation: Legal Deposit & Open Access Books, Archiving and Digitally Preserving PhD Theses, and the Copim Open Archiving Criteria. These recommendations have been documented by the project in a Policy Recommendations report and are available as separate briefings. Below are the policy recommendations, based on the findings of this report. These recommendations are intended for National Libraries themselves, when addressing institutional policies and procedures, as well as for legislators in their national contexts. They also involve incidental recommendations for publishers preparing and depositing OA monographs.

1. Legal deposit open access monographs should remain openly available under their original licence

For open access content to be openly available the original published content (files) should be freely available to view and download by any reader with access to the internet through the National Library's catalogue. This recommendation is intended for National Libraries.

2. The open access status of a legal deposit open access monograph/associated deposited item should be clearly recorded in the associated metadata and catalogue records

This recommendation relates to findings in the research that in some cases when an open access monograph was deposited with a National Library the open access status was either not recorded in the associated metadata, or there was no clear field for this information to be provided to National Libraries. Clear and openly accessible information of the open access status of a monograph is not only important in the immediate deposit and availability of open access monographs, but also incredibly important in the long-term preservation of this status both for future generations and if the open access monograph is reproduced and made available in other contexts. This recommendation is intended directly for National Libraries but should also be reflected in the information provided to publishers about how to complete the metadata field recommended above. We recommend National Libraries work with metadata standards organisations to ensure a consistency of approach.

3. Open access licencing relating to the usage conditions of open access monographs, such as Creative Commons licences, should be documented and clearly displayed in cataloguing information

This recommendation relates to the findings in the research that licences such as Creative Commons licences were not always clearly displayed in the cataloguing information of an open access monograph and that the onus was on the user to find this information within the publication itself or from the publisher. However clearly displayed licencing is important when considering not only the preservation of the open access status of an open access monograph, but also in archiving how these usage conditions may have changed or been altered over time. Again, we recommend National Libraries work with metadata standards organisations to ensure a consistency of approach.

4. Electronic legal deposit legislation should be passed for all National Libraries by their correlating government

This recommendation relates to the finding in one case that electronic legal deposit legislation had not been passed in the National Library's national context. Electronic legal deposit is incredibly important for open access monographs not only because by their nature open access publications will include a digital edition, but also because electronic deposit is what allows for

these digital editions to be available to openly view and use online. This recommendation is intended for international governments and legislators.

5. All National Libraries should have a mechanism for the open display and download of approved content associated with open access monographs and this should link to other records for the same work within the National Library systems and catalogue

This recommendation is related to Copim's Open Archiving principles, which were developed by the work package on Archiving and Digital Preservation (Cole, Gatti and Mitcham 2026). Specifically, it is related to the principle that digital preservation platforms should be adopted to enable the open display and download of content. It also relates to the principle that there should be an openly available audit trail for each individual monograph, and that this is all provided in one place. This relates to the overarching philosophy of Open Book Future's policy recommendations that digital preservation practice should be more transparent. This recommendation is intended for the National Libraries themselves, whilst recognising that each individual context will have its own challenges. However, this recommendation is also intended to aid the sharing of practice with other National Libraries, which was found in the research to be a way of furthering digital preservation practice.

12. Conclusion

Considering the findings of this report, the discussion and the recommendations for policy, this conclusion summarises these elements and suggests some further avenues for research and actions to be taken.

12.1 Digital Preservation and Challenges Faced

One of the key findings of this report is the time, effort and resources required by National Libraries to identify and acquire publications relevant to their collection policies despite the existence of legal deposit legislation, detailed in the discussion section of this report in ‘The Steps Before Ingest’. This has been an unexpected finding, but given the wide range of organisations, publishers and individuals that publish materials relevant to national collections it is not surprising that this is the case. The extent to which National Libraries collaborate with publishers/depositors and the different mechanisms they have developed to identify relevant content highlights the extent to which many legal deposit laws need to be reviewed in the context of new technologies and the diverse nature of the publishing eco-system, particularly with regard to OA monographs. Current approaches to identifying relevant content are thorough and systematic, but there is scope for more automated processes and indeed many of the participating National Libraries are exploring technological solutions to identifying content on a large scale.

Identifying content is an area where the establishment of a forum or network could facilitate knowledge sharing of such large-scale automated approaches to identifying content. This aligns with findings from the wider digital preservation community that digital preservation is most successful when there is thorough documentation between all stakeholders and good practice has been shared ahead of time, and is signposted in the Digital Preservation Coalition’s EDRMS Preservation Toolkit (Digital Preservation Coalition 2021). It also emphasises the challenge for National Libraries in that good practice in digital preservation is not just about their own internal systems, but also how they encourage the good practice and documentation of those depositing. Whilst this posits an interesting element in establishing the role of the National Library, it also suggests that a potential further avenue for this research would be to map the process for how publishers and individual depositors prepare their monographs for legal deposit and further digital preservation.

National libraries operate within a global ecosystem; an element of that ecosystem are the commercial systems that libraries use as part of their own infrastructure and information management systems. There are several major catalogue record aggregators and metadata suppliers that National Libraries use to create basic catalogue records for the items in their legal deposit / national collections. Whilst these aggregators are international in scope and support the full spectrum of writing systems their interfaces and the records they are scraping tend to be in

the English language, either original or transliterated. Where records and metadata have been transliterated from a different writing system this can make it challenging for libraries to obtain a comprehensive overview of items that have been originally written in a non-roman language. When it comes to digital preservation, where systems are operating across socio-linguistic borders, this poses a challenge for National Libraries. In the context of this report, this specifically posed a challenge for the discovery and identification of open access monographs in Arabic. This suggests that an area for further research would not only be investigating the extent of this challenge, but also how it impacts on the identification and ingest of open access monographs in languages other than English.

12.2 Open Access Monographs

Although this report is focussed on the digital preservation of legal deposit OA monographs, it should be acknowledged that in the UK context at least, open access publications likely do not represent a large percentage of what is being digitally preserved through legal deposit. This accounts for some of the findings in this report around open access documentation and challenges, addressed in the discussion section of this report in as realistically there will not have been numerous cases of open access publications being deposited with National Libraries. However, whilst open access publications may not represent a large number of monographs, they do represent an increasing proportion of research literature, as evidenced in UK Research and Innovation's (UKRI) open access policy⁶. This suggests that the amount of legal deposit OA monographs that will be received by National Libraries is only going to increase. Therefore, it is important that National Libraries anticipate this in their digital preservation processes through prioritising discussions around the digital preservation of OA monographs in networks and forums, and by addressing the recommendations within this report, particularly in regard to preserving open access status through metadata, licencing and online availability.

This point about the co-existence of OA monographs and closed access monographs raises a question around whether National Libraries need a parallel route for OA monographs, as is detailed in the National Library of Scotland case study, or whether they should focus on improving processes that do both, as is detailed in the British Library and Library and Archives Canada case studies. This comparison of workflows is detailed to an extent in this report, however a more in-depth review of this would be not only an area for further research, but an area for further discussion and sharing of practice amongst National Libraries.

12.3 National Library Networks

As reviewed in the background context section of this report, National Libraries are both widely engaged in sharing practice through networks, but also in a position outside of these networks to advocate on issues of digital preservation and open access. Within the case studies this advocacy

role is modelled by several of the participants, whether this is in the case Qatar National Library funding the publication of OA monographs, or through the outreach strategies detailed by the National Library of Scotland and Library and Archives Canada. As well as evidencing the evolving role of National Libraries beyond capturing legal deposit publications, this advocacy also poses another point of discussion within National Library networks and forums.

When considering the notion of a National Library Network to address the challenges of digitally preserving OA monographs, the earlier points about the time, effort and resources required by National Libraries in this process inevitably suggest that a dedicated network that regularly meets would bring its own challenges. However, given the existing networks and organisations through which National Libraries share practice, such as CENL and the IFLA, there is certainly scope for these discussions to be a part of existing events and forums. We therefore suggest that the findings and resources of this report, as well as the policy recommendations herein, form the basis of these discussions and an agenda towards improving practice in the digital preservation of OA monographs.

13. Bibliography

Aramburo, A. S. (2019). The future of national libraries. *Alexandria: The Journal of National and International Library and Information Issues*, 29(3), 225-227.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0955749019892373>

Barnes, M., Bell, E., Cole, G., Fry, J., Gatti, R., & Stone, G. (2022). WP7 Scoping Report on Archiving and Preserving OA Monographs (1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6725309>

Barnes, M. (2024). The OBF National Libraries Network: a summary of our first year. *Copim*.
<https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.dd03d609>

Brazier, C. (2016). Great libraries? Good libraries? Digital collection development and what it means for our great research collections. In: Baker, D. and Evans, W. ed. *Digital Information Strategies: From Applications and Content to Libraries and People*. Chandos Publishing (pp. 41–56). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100251-3.00003-2>

Brindley, D. (2009). Challenges for Great Libraries in the Age of the Digital Native. *Information Services and Use*, 29, 3-12 <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-2009-0594>

Cole, G., Gatti, R., and Mitcham, J. (2026, March 16). What should open archiving look like for open access publications?. CILIP Metadata and Discovery Group Conference 2026 (MDG), Bristol, UK. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19049034>

De Beer M, Van der Merwe M, Ball L, Fourie I (2016), "Legal deposit of electronic books – a review of challenges faced by national libraries". *Library Hi Tech*, Vol. 34 No. 1 pp. 87–103.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-06-2015-0060>

Digital Preservation Coalition (2021). *EDRMS Preservation Toolkit*.
<http://doi.org/10.7207/edrmstoolkit21-01>

Gooding, P. and Terras, M. (2019) 'An Ark to Save Learning from Deluge'? Reconceptualising Legal Deposit After the Digital Turn. In: Gooding, P. and Terras, M. eds. *Electronic Legal Deposit: Shaping the Library Collections of the Future*. Facet Studies in Information Science. Facet; 2019:203-228.
<https://doi.org/10.29085/9781783303786>

Hagerlid, J. (2011). "The role of the national library as a catalyst for an open access agenda: the experience in Sweden". *Interlending & Document Supply*, Vol. 39 No. 2 pp. 115–118.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02641611111138923>

Horstmann, W. (2017). From collecting to connecting – the role of libraries in Open Access. In K. Söllner & B. Mittermaier (Eds.), *Praxishandbuch Open Access* (1st ed., pp. 62–74). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110494068-008>

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), (2024, November 20). Legal Deposit: A Strategic Tool for Building Tomorrow's Heritage. The National Library of Singapore, Online. <https://www.ifla.org/news/ifla-national-libraries-section-organises-webinar-on-legal-deposit-a-strategic-tool-for-building-tomorrows-heritage/>

Morrison, H., and Desautels, L. (2016). Open access, copyright and licensing: basics for open access publishers. *Journal of orthopaedic case reports*, 6(1), 1–2.
<https://doi.org/10.13107/jocr.2250-0685.360>

Oehlschläger, S., and Wenzel, A. (2025) Digital Cultural Heritage or: E-Legal Deposit in European National Libraries. Conference of European National Librarians (CENL)

Pedley, P. (2019). Legal Deposit. In *Essential Law for Information Professionals* (pp. 99–106). Chapter, Facet.

Stephens, A., & Gibby, R. (2011). National Implementations of Electronic Legal Deposit. *Alexandria: The Journal of National and International Library and Information Issues*, 22(1), 53-67. <https://doi.org/10.7227/ALX.22.1.6>

Stephens, A. (2016). Functions, tasks and roles of national libraries in the 21st century. *Alexandria: The Journal of National and International Library and Information Issues*, 26(2), 145-198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0955749016653031>

Suber, P. (2008). Gratis and Libre Open Access. *SPARC Open Access Newsletter*.
<https://sparcopen.org/our-work/gratis-and-libre-open-access/>

World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works: Paris Act of July 24 1971, as amended on September 28 1979. Geneva: World Intellectual Property Organization; 1995.

14. Appendices

Appendix 1 – British Library Monograph Ingest Process Map

British Library Monograph Ingest Process

Appendix 2 – Library and Archives Canada Monograph Ingest Process Map

Library and Archives Canada Monograph Ingest Process

Appendix 3 – Qatar National Library Monograph Ingest Process Map

Appendix 4 – The National Library of Scotland Monograph Ingest Process Map

Appendix 5 – The National Library of the Czech Republic Monograph Ingest Process Map

National Library of the Czech Republic Monograph Ingest Process

Phase	Identify	Aquire	Pre-ingest	Ingest	Repository	Preservation	Access
Publisher							
Department of Acquisitions	Start: Contact publishers to make aware of electronic deposit system to receive works	Document: Agreement with publishers: what can do with the works, what can receive, the formats NLCR will accept are included in the agreement					
Electronic Submission System			Data: Receives information from the publisher, data which will help to produce the metadata.	Publisher also submits the publication files. This automatically produces a cataloguing record and a metadata record either using the existing ISBN or the information provided by the publisher			
Library System (ALEPH)				Cataloguing and metadata record received	ALEPH connects to the electronic submission system, LTP system, and the Digital Library		ALEPH record links to access in the Digital Library
NLCR Processing System (Several teams involved)				This workflow involves the Department of Acquisition, the Department of the ISBN, and the Department of Cataloguing. It involves checking accessibility and preservability, and giving electronic deposits their persistent identifier.			
Department of Post-Processing				After the processing workflow, the Department of Post-Processing will transform the metadata and enhance the records			
Digital Preservation Standards Department	Information sent ahead of publisher agreement: What file formats are good for preservation and how preserved, this information is also on the website.			Metadata is enhanced for use in the Digital Library. These enhancements are for searching purposes and otherwise the data is kept the same.		For preservation purposes, three copies of digital publications are kept on magnetic tapes. An online copy, an offline copy and a geographically distanced copy.	
Long-term Preservation System				Preservation copy received			
Digital Library				Access copy received			In the Digital Library the access is set – either public/private. Publicly accessible publications can be viewed online. All records can also be viewed in the Digital Library.
Notes	Scope of publications includes: Czech author, published in Czech or topic about Czech lives (could be published elsewhere)	Formats accepted include: PDF/A, PDF/A 1a, PDF/A 1b, PDF/A 2a, PDF/A 2b, PDF/A 2u and EPUB 2.0.1 – this information is provided in handbooks on NLCR website and sent ahead of the acquisition phase.	Custom electronic submission system created for NL CR	Currently, it is only possible to upload one publication at a time. NLCR are preparing for publishers to request the ability to submit multiple publications.	ALEPH custom made by supplier	Long term preservation system also custom built	Digital Library a CR open source system. New version of Digital Library will distinguish between other licences such as Creative Commons etc.